

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE OF MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the effective organization of mother tongue and reading literacy classes in primary grades. It is discussed that it is necessary to read correctly, increase vocabulary, and teach broad thinking to improve students' literacy.*

Keywords: *personality, good thought, good deed, good word, innovation, creativity, free thinking, speech culture, lesson efficiency.*

INTRODUCTION

First of all, in improving the literacy of students, in learning a number of features such as correct reading, increasing vocabulary, teaching broad thinking, improving speech, consciousness, improving the native language and reading literacy. it is necessary to know how to organize. One of the main tasks of mother tongue and reading literacy is to develop one's mind, to teach to think, to educate a child with a healthy mind for the future. It is especially important that the transition from simple words to complex words in the expansion of the child's mind is based on the state educational standards in accordance with age characteristics. Being able to organize lessons correctly and effectively increases the effectiveness of studying, and is another way to get spiritual nourishment.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said the right thing when he said in his speeches [1]: "A child who reads one book today will lead a child who has watched ten TV sets tomorrow." Because today, a child who enriches his knowledge, spirituality, and psyche by reading one book, learns to think independently and freely, and expands his worldview thanks to the information he reads, will tomorrow watch various entertainment programs, low-level series, and cartoons on TV. He will have more opportunities to find his place in life than his peers who are only learning to imitate them. One of the urgent tasks of today is to teach our children to read so that they can grow up to become mature experts in a certain field in life, to become citizens who make a worthy contribution to the development of the Motherland. Teaching children to read is the duty of teachers together with parents.

LITERATURE REVIEW

It is no secret to any of us that the reforms being carried out in our country, especially the fundamental changes in the field of education, are for the education of the young generation who are fully mature, well-rounded and think independently. For this, in order to improve the quality of education, it is necessary to establish the "State Education Standard", to pay strong attention to the issues of education in primary classes, and in this way to teachers and pedagogues. Several requirements are being made. As the first President said: "Teachers, who are responsible for the education of a well-rounded person, which is a priority area of state policy, are responsible for the development of our society today. Entrusted with the responsibility of training 21st century

personnel who know their profession perfectly". Formation of a perfect personality is placed on the agenda as an important social task of every era.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the teaching of mother tongue and literature in the first and second grades, it is a special task to develop a conscious approach, self-expression and communication skills, as well as the ability to listen, speak, read and write, taking into account the individual abilities of students.

And in Uzbekistan, the types of speech activities acquired by the student with the help of language teaching: listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing are taught in each class, the ability to exchange ideas independently, to understand the text heard, to get information by reading written sources, to express one's reaction to events.

There is another case where the language of education in a particular class or school is determined by the decisions of the students and their parents within the framework of the law on education. However, if necessary, mother tongue and literature classes may be combined according to the government's decision. In this case, teachers must pass at least half of all subjects taught in the language designated as their mother tongue. In this process, a mutual agreement between the family and the school is followed [2].

Educational technologies cover a certain field of pedagogical activity. Building the stages of the didactic process in a certain sequence means organizing the educational activities of students with the help of selected teaching methods in accordance with the goals set on the subject. A modern approach to improving the quality of education in primary classes - according to its essence and content, is based on a certain pedagogical theory and belongs to one or another classification. When thinking about their effectiveness, it is possible to see how far the goal of all educational institutions is being achieved, which is able to trace the teaching process and direct it purposefully, to ensure the cooperative activity of the teacher and the student.

Currently, education is conducted in seven languages in general secondary education schools. In particular, in 2 thousand 69 schools, education is conducted in Russian, Karakalpak, Kazakh, Tajik, Turkmen, and Kyrgyz languages, and necessary conditions have been created for representatives of each nationality based on the principle of international tolerance. The educational process is organized in the students' native language, and each of these schools has textbooks and educational methodical literature for all subjects [3].

Conducting the lesson on the basis of innovative technologies further increases the effectiveness of the lesson. Also, a number of methods, including [4]:

"Brainstorming" method; "Cluster" method;

"Venn diagram" method; "Black box" method;

"B B B" method.

Kamola Sadiq's daughter's "Who do we call a neighbor?" Let's look at the story:

WHO DO WE SAY NEIGHBOR?

Grandfather: "Son, did you go to our neighbor Aunt Farida's house and help her with the housework?"

Temur: - Grandfather, do you mean Abdullah's grandmother at the beginning of the street? Their houses are far away, can we call them neighbors too?

Grandfather: - My son, forty yards in front of our house, forty yards behind it, forty yards on the left side, forty yards on the right side of our house are all our neighbors.

Temur: - Wow...

Grandfather: - Don't forget to get along with your neighbors now and when you grow up.
Do not shy away from doing good to them!

Temur: - Of course I will! Kamola Sadiq's daughter

The story is read by the first teacher and the students are asked the following questions.

1 Who do we call neighbors?

2 Do you agree with what Temur's grandfather said? What for?

3 What should be done to get along with the neighbors?

4 How can you do something good for people in your neighborhood?

Then the story will be explained by the teacher, then read the dialogue again, as it says in the task: One of you is a grandfather and the other is a child with your partner. Pronounce words clearly and correctly.

Students are evaluated and encouraged. Methods and methods determine the quality of the educational process. It also has an impact on the student's conscious and strong mastering and the development of activity. The ability of the teacher to choose the right methods and methods depends on the subject taught in the lesson. If one method is used for the statement of a new topic, another method is used to strengthen and generalize it. "Truly, to influence the student's spirituality and morals, to educate him as a perfect person, it is not enough to read and teach fiction. In this way, a personal example and the ability to apply what you have learned in practice are also of great importance" [5].

CONCLUSION

In short, the present time requires the teacher to be creative, free-thinking, to work on the basis of new technologies. the high level of pedagogical experience, the formation of communication culture, the culture of speech, the presence of self-management ability, the manifestation of knowledge, skills and competence, show that he has pedagogical skills. The effectiveness of the lesson depends on the skill of the teacher.

In conclusion, it should be said that a specialist teacher teaching the subject of the mother tongue should pay great attention to teaching his lessons with the help of new pedagogical technologies. Effective organization of mother tongue classes in schools is of fundamental importance for the development of our language in the future.

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